

H²IOSC

Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud

CALL	<p>Ministry of University and Research (MUR), Directorate-General for Internationalization and Communication, Notice D.D. 3264 dated 28/12/2021.</p> <p>Mission 4 "Education and Research" - Component 2 "From research to enterprise" - Investment Line 3.1 "Fund for the realization of an integrated system of research and innovation infrastructure", Action 3.1.1 "Creation of new IRs or strengthening of existing ones that contribute to Horizon Europe's Scientific Excellence objectives and networking"</p>
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ABSTRACT

This deliverable reports the management processes for communication, monitoring, approval of deliverables, administration, ethics, data access policy, IP management, quality plan adopted within the H2IOSC project, including the setting up of guidelines, templates and standards.

It also provides the necessary indications to define the overall managerial strategy of how each phase established by the H2IOSC documentation must be made operational, with a dedicated timeframe, during the project implementation.

The current text constitutes an updated version of Deliverable D1.1 (previous versions published in Bimesters I and VI) in which the relevant activities launched in order to ensure the proper and timely implementation of H2IOSC activities were described.

The document must be read together with other project deliverables referred to in the text in consideration of the overlapping treatment of some topics.

Table of Contents

<u>LIST OF ACRONYMS.....</u>	<u>5</u>
<u>LIST OF FIGURES.....</u>	<u>7</u>
<u>LIST OF TABLES.....</u>	<u>8</u>
<u>1. INTRODUCTION.....</u>	<u>9</u>
<u>2. THE PROJECT.....</u>	<u>9</u>
2.1 THE H2IOSC CONSORTIUM.....	10
2.2 THE H2IOSC BUDGET.....	10
2.3 THE H2IOSC STRUCTURE.....	11
<u>3. COMMUNICATION.....</u>	<u>12</u>
3.1 COMMUNICATION WITHIN THE PROJECT.....	12
3.1.1 EMAIL AND MAILING LISTS.....	12
3.1.2 CONFERENCE CALLS.....	13
3.1.3 MICROSOFT TEAMS™.....	14
3.2 GENERAL MEETING.....	15
3.3 EDITORIAL BOARD.....	15
3.4 PUBLICITY AND VISUAL IDENTITY.....	16
3.5 OUTREACH – THE H2IOSC WEBPAGE.....	16
<u>4. MANAGEMENT AND ADMINISTRATION.....</u>	<u>17</u>
4.1 DECISION MAKING.....	17
4.2 THE INTERNAL AGREEMENT.....	18
4.3 GUIDELINES FOR THE RECRUITMENT OF PERSONNEL.....	19
4.4 DOCUMENTS AND TEMPLATES FOR THE NRRP PROCUREMENT PROCEDURES.....	19
<u>5. MONITORING.....</u>	<u>20</u>
5.1 INTEGRATED SYSTEM FOR THE ACCOUNTING MANAGEMENT.....	21
5.2 SHAREPOINT WORKBOOK.....	21
5.3 OWNCLOUD REPOSITORY.....	22
5.4 SCIENTIFIC REPOSITORY.....	23
<u>6. REPORTING.....</u>	<u>25</u>

6.1	CHECKLISTS (ANNEX 6 AND 7)	25
6.2	REPORTING FACTSHEET	25
6.3	TIMESHEET	25
6.4	WORKFLOW	26
6.4.1	PROCEDURAL WORKFLOW	27
6.4.2	FINANCIAL WORKFLOW	27
6.4.3	PHYSICAL WORKFLOW	28
7.	<u>ETHICS POLICY</u>	31
8.	<u>DATA ACCESS POLICY</u>	32
9.	<u>IP MANAGEMENT ORGANIZATION</u>	33
10.	<u>QUALITY PLAN</u>	38
11.	<u>CONCLUSIONS</u>	41
12.	<u>REFERENCES</u>	41

LIST OF ACRONYMS

AMB	Administrative Management Board
CC 0	The Creative Commons No Rights Reserved license, which means that the rightsholder(s) waives its copyrights in the work so it is left in the public domain.
CC BY	The CC BY open licence which allows everyone to re-use, distribute and modify the licensed materials. The licence requires users to give credit (attribution) to the creator.
CC BY-NC	The CC BY-NC licence is the same as the CC BY with the added restriction that any derivative work must be for non-commercial use only.
CC BY-NC-SA	The CC BY-NC-SA licence is the same as the CC BY-NC taking into account that remix, transform, or build upon the material, imply that the contributions must be distributed under the same license as the original.
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (National Research Council)
CUP	Codice Unico di Progetto (Unique Project Code)
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DNSH	Do No Significant Harm
DSU	Dipartimento di Scienze umane e sociali, patrimonio culturale
EAB	External Advisory Board
EB	Editorial Board
ECCCH	European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage
EC	European Commission
ECHOES	European Colonial Heritage Modalities in Entangled Cities
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
GCT	Technical Coordination Group

H2IOSC	Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud
ICDI	Italian Computing and Data Infrastructure
IO	Intermediate Objective
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
MIC	Ministero della Cultura
MUR	Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca (Ministry of University and Research)
NRRP	National Recovery and Resilience Plan
OPERAS	Open scholarly communication in the European research area for social sciences and humanities
OU	Operating Unit
PMB	Project Management Board
PNIR	Piano Nazionale Infrastrutture di Ricerca (National Research Infrastructure Program)
RI	Research Infrastructure
RIC	Research Infrastructure Coordinator
SCI	Social and Cultural Innovation
SIGLA	Sistema Informativo per la Gestione delle Linee di Attività
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud
UTS	Unit of purpose
WP	Work Package

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1- WPs inter-relation	11
Figure 2 - The PNRR-IR H2IOSC ADMINISTRATIVE TEAM	14
Figure 3 - The H2IOSC Workspace in Microsoft Teams™	14
Figure 4 - H2IOSC logo	16
Figure 5 - H2IOSC webpage sections	17
Figure 6 - NRRP Procurement templates CNR	20
Figure 7 - H2IOSC Gantt chart	21
Figure 8 - OwnCloud repository structure	23
Figure 9 – Microsoft Teams Workspace	24
Figure 10 - Microsoft Teams Repository	24
Figure 11 - General structure of the Timesheet file.....	26
Figure 12 – Procedural workflow	27
Figure 13 - Financial workflow	28
Figure 14 – Deliverables workflow.....	29
Figure 15 – Bimonthly reports workflow	30
Figure 16 – Six-months reports workflow	30
Figure 17 – Intellectual Property Rights.....	33
Figure 18 –Timeline questionnaires.....	40

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 - M2C2I3.1 allocation.....	9
Table 2 - H2IOSC budget	11
Table 3 - The webpage structure.....	17

1. INTRODUCTION

In the framework of the implementation of Mission 4, "Education and Research" - Component 2, "From research to enterprise" - Investment Line 3.1, "Fund for the realization of an integrated system of research and innovation infrastructure", Action 3.1. 1 "Creation of new RIs or strengthening of existing ones that contribute to Horizon Europe's Scientific Excellence objectives and networking" with Notice Directorial Decree 3264 of 28th December 2021 the Ministry of University and Research of Italy (MUR) issued a competitive call for the strengthening and creation of Research Infrastructures within the framework of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP).

The funding aims at creating or strengthening Research Infrastructures (RIs) identified as High or Medium Priority in the National Research Infrastructure Program (PNIR), as well as the creation of thematic or multidisciplinary networks of existing RIs, again from among those identified as High or Medium Priority in the PNIR.

The available resources for the action sum to 1.080M€ distributed by ESFRI areas as follows:

ESFRI Area	Total allocation
DIGIT	€ 90.000.000,00
Energy	€ 90.000.000,00
Environment	€ 200.000.000,00
Health and Food	€ 200.000.000,00
Physical Sciences and Engineering	€ 400.000.000,00
Social and Cultural Innovation	€ 100.000.000,00

Table 1 - M2C2I3.1 allocation

Actions eligible for funding had to be aimed at implementing one of the following types of intervention:

1. enhancement of PNIR high priority RI;
2. creation of new PNIR high and medium priority RI;
3. creation of thematic or multidisciplinary networks of existing PNIR high and medium priority RI indicating the main theme for multidisciplinary networks among the ESFRI Areas.

In this context, the National Research Council of Italy (CNR) has been awarded a € 41.696.877,08 grant to implement the "Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud - H2IOSC" project.

2. THE PROJECT

H2IOSC supports the implementation of a coherent strategy for RIs development and integration in Italy, optimizing the use of the most relevant assets, upgrading, and implementing the facilities. It foresees the collaboration of the Italian nodes of 2 ESFRI Landmarks in Social and Cultural Innovation (CLARIN and DARIAH) and 2 ESFRI Projects in the same domain (E-RIHS and OPERAS). All the four national nodes of the above RIs are led by CNR and are strategic and considered of "High Priority" within the national policies and roadmap (PNIR). H2IOSC aims at creating the Italian Cloud Network for research in humanities,

linguistics and heritage science, a federated and inclusive cluster of RIs in the ESFRI domain of Social and Cultural Innovation to allow researchers from various disciplines in the Humanities, Language technologies and the Cultural Heritage sectors to collaborate in data and computing intensive research.

H2IOSC services addresses the needs of a vast range of disciplines in the SCI spectrum and possibly beyond. The project also elaborates priorities for the resources onboarding process in the integrated environment. Each participating RI works towards reaching the maturity threshold set by the project as entry point, as a prerequisite for the actual alignment and integration of the selected assets within the federation. To promote accessibility and realize the FAIR approach, a one-stop, easy-entry place is going to be created, where users will find tools, datasets, services, and pilot projects supporting specific needs of domain and cross-domain research scenarios. H2IOSC promotes a data centric approach, where resources are available in an integrated environment accessible through a set of Virtual and Remote access methods. It also fosters training and engagement activities to build FAIR and Open Science skills, boosts the visibility of RIs at national and international level, creates new profiles (e.g.: data stewards, data curators) supporting digital processes in research and in the Cultural and Creative Industries.

2.1 The H2IOSC Consortium

The CNR is the single beneficiary Institution of the project, with a research team composed of 12 Institutes and 18 Operating Units, namely:

1. Istituto Opera del Vocabolario Italiano (OVI), with its Pisa and Florence branches
2. Istituto di Scienze del Patrimonio Culturale (ISPC), with its Lecce, Catania, Naples, Florence, Rome and Milan branches
3. Istituto per il lessico intellettuale europeo e storia delle idee (ILIESI)
4. Istituto di linguistica computazionale "Antonio Zampolli" (ILC)
5. Istituto Nazionale di Ottica (INO)
6. Istituto di Storia del Pensiero Filosofico (ISPF)
7. Istituto di Scienze e Tecnologie Chimiche "Giulio Natta" (SCITEC)
8. Istituto per le applicazioni del calcolo "Mauro Picone" (IAC)
9. Istituto di scienza e tecnologie dell'informazione "Alessandro Faedo" (ISTI)
10. Istituto di Calcolo e Reti ad Alte Prestazioni (ICAR)
11. Istituto di Nanotecnologia (NANOTEC)
12. Istituto di Matematica Applicata e Tecnologie Informatiche "Enrico Magenes" (IMATI)

2.2 The H2IOSC Budget

In line with the call eligibility criteria and the three horizontal priorities (youth, gender equality and territorial cohesion) of the NRRP, the total budget of the project was built up as shown in the table below.

COSTS (€) ENTIRE PROJECT			
	Costs included in the request for funding		
	To be located within the eight southern Regions	To be located outside the eight southern Regions	Total requested grant
a. Fixed term personnel specifically hired for the project	3.070.780,00 €	5.260.720,00 €	8.331.500,00 €
b. Scientific instrumentation and technological equipment, software licenses and patent	13.773.000,00 €	10.829.000,00 €	24.602.000,00 €
c. Open Access, Trans-National Access, FAIR principles implementation	799.000,00 €	2.272.344,00 €	3.071.344,00 €
d. Civil infrastructures and related systems	795.500,00 €	530.000,00 €	1.325.500,00 €
e. Indirect costs, including running costs	1.331.839,60 €	1.395.993,48 €	2.727.833,08 €
f. Training activities	588.000,00 €	1.050.700,00 €	1.638.700,00 €
Total	20.358.119,60 €	21.338.757,48 €	41.696.877,08 €

Table 2- H2IOSC budget

2.3 The H2IOSC Structure

The 8 WPs that build the structure of the project are: WP1. Project and Financial Management, Quality Assurance; WP2. Landscaping & building communities; WP3. Digital Resources Standardization, Consolidation & Alignment; WP4. RIs Nodes and Resources Interoperability; WP5. Marketplace; WP6. Resources Accessibility: Servification, Virtualization, Remotization; WP7. Community pilots: innovative cross-domain services and environments; WP8. Training, Capacity Building, Engagement. Their interaction is shown in the Figure 1, below:

Figure 1- WPs inter-relation

WP1 provides full administrative support for all the H2IOSC Activities and WPs and acts as interface with the funding Ministry, MUR. It also addresses relationships between the project and other external stakeholders, puts in place the project agreements, ensures compliance with the ministerial and NRRP's rules and reporting requirements; eventually it addresses short, medium and long term sustainability issues for the project and its results.

In this framework, several actions have been put in place in order to comply with the above-mentioned objectives.

3. COMMUNICATION

For the purpose of the project coordination and reporting, H2IOSC has put in place a set of internal and external communication tools and procedures.

The project has relied on a dedicated - self hosted - mail server, a number of dedicated mailing lists, a collaboration platform (Microsoft Teams™) as well as CnrBox: an open source, self-hosted and cloud-based storage solution for the management of documents based on OwnCloud¹, allowing for a most efficient communication among the partners. It has also set up a publicity kit based on the official guidelines for the actions of information and communication by the implementing subjects and a project webpage.

3.1 Communication within the Project

The project communication flow has been managed at three different levels: with the MUR, with the CNR headquarters and within the project consortium.

The Scientific Coordinator, the Infrastructure Manager and the Financial Officer have the hub of these processes.

The regulations, guidelines and information spread by the Ministry have been regularly forwarded to the project partners, accompanied by explanation notes and, when necessary, follow up meetings.

The interface with the CNR headquarters aims at ensuring and strengthening a coherent set of procedures, shared by all the Institutes beneficiaries of NRRP funding.

3.1.1 Email and mailing lists

In order to ensure a smooth, efficient and extensive communication among the project partners, several tools have been implemented. A set of mailing lists have been created addressing the participants as detailed below:

H2IOSC – General (addressed to all the project participants): reaching all the project participants, it is used for spreading information of general interest related to administrative issues, management rules, MUR directives and guidelines, communication from the central administration of the CNR, meetings, minutes, general requests, project templates and guidelines.

H2IOSC – Administrative contacts (addressed to the administrative staff): reaching people involved in administrative issues, it is used to communicate with the staff in charge of the

¹ <https://cloud.cnr.it/owncloud/>

recruiting and purchasing procedures. Guidelines on the recruitment procedures, guidelines on purchase procedures, DNSH documents, procedural and financial advancement fact sheets, templates of the checklists to the periodic report, have been produced and transferred to the OUs.

WP Leaders: Reaching the 8 WP Leaders (and their deputies), it is mainly used to manage scientific content and monitor the timely implementation of project deliverables and reports to handle conflict and eventually troubleshooting.

H2IOSC GCT: the Technical Coordination Group (GCT), composed by members chosen by the OUs of the project consortium, oversees defining the technical subset of common requirements that will ensure interoperability not only within each Research Infrastructure, but especially among the four different Infrastructures that H2IOSC federates.

H2IOSC Coordinators of the RIs Italian Nodes: reaching the coordinators of the Italian Nodes of E-RIHS, DARIAH, OPERAS and CLARIN for relevant strategic issues.

H2IOSC Editorial Board: reaching the referents of E-RIHS, DARIAH, OPERAS and CLARIN for communication issues.

3.1.2 Conference Calls

A regular monthly **plenary** meeting is held on the first Monday of each month in order to discuss issues of general interest on both scientific and administrative aspects of the project. OUs are expected to report on the advances of their activities as well as on potential criticalities and troubleshooting of technical and organisational problems managed with the support of the Project Management of H2IOSC (Scientific Coordinator, Infrastructure Manager, Financial Officer).

The **Coordinators of the RIs Italian Nodes** meet at least once a month, with the Infrastructure Manager, to update the project strategy and manage possible criticalities.

The **technical coordination group** meets regularly on the second and fourth Wednesday of each month, and in any case whenever the need arises, to discuss tech-related issues relating to RIs within H2IOSC project and share possible solutions. During the meeting, reports on the activities of the infrastructures at the H2IOSC project level are illustrated.

The **WP Leaders** group meets regularly on the first and third Wednesday of each month, and in any case whenever the need arises, to ensure early detection of any problems, delays, and to take appropriate measures to manage possible risks. Furthermore, the WP Leaders group processes any input coming from the RIs Coordinators and the Technical Coordination Group, providing adequate support to the decision-making process needed to keep the project physical progress aligned to the H2IOSC shared objectives. During the meetings, each WP leader is requested to briefly present its contribution according to the objectives, as initially planned, and to give a status report of the WP activities and progress.

The **WP** participants meet usually once a week to plan and monitor their activities and update on the progress and possible criticalities.

The **Editorial Board** components meet usually once a week to plan and monitor their activities.

Finally, the Financial Officer and the Infrastructure Manager, also give constant online support on legal, financial, and administrative issues to the OUs on a one-by-one basis. Tool mostly used for these calls is Microsoft Teams™.

All the regular meetings discussions and outcomes are transcribed, and the meetings minutes are stored in the shared drive folders, for future reference and documentation.

3.1.3 Microsoft Teams™

Support and ongoing interaction have been granted to the administrative staff in charge of managing the daily procedures in the H2IOSC OUs through the creation of a dedicated team in the Microsoft Teams™ application.

Figure 2 - The PNRR-IR H2IOSC ADMINISTRATIVE TEAM

The use of this tool allows to enhance cooperation and share in real time information, documents, ideas, and approaches to problem-solving, thus avoiding the duplication of efforts and allowing to share best practices with all the H2IOSC participants.

Figure 3 - The H2IOSC Workspace in Microsoft Teams™

3.2 General meeting

On 6 and 7 February 2024, the project General Meeting entitled "The project partnership meets stakeholders" (<https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/h2iosc-general-meeting/>) was held in Rome, at the CNR headquarters. During the first day the following talks were scheduled:

- Opening Remarks with the participation of the President of the CNR, the Director of the DSU and the RUP of the MUR;
- Joining forces to build H2IOSC: E-RIHS, CLARIN, OPERAS, DARIAH. Needs, expectations, outcomes with the interventions of the four RIs coordinators;
- H2IOSC Enabling New Generation Research: Champions with four interventions corresponding to the four champions identified for the RIs;
- H2IOSC in the National and International RIs Landscape with interventions related to EOSC, SSHOC Open Cluster, MIC Digital Library and ECCCH-ECHOES.

The second day of the meeting was, however, focused first on H2IOSC progress: problems, processes, results with the interventions of the Scientific Coordinator, the Infrastructure Manager and the Financial Manager for a general overview of the project and then with the interventions of the WP Leaders for the scientific progress of the WPs.

In the afternoon of the same day, the first meeting between the Project Management Board and the External Advisory Board was held in which the objectives and progress of the project were briefly described and the mandate assigned to the latter Board was described.

3.3 Editorial Board

The Editorial board was established to have, in effect, a communications office for the H2IOSC federation. Its official members come from each involved research infrastructure.

In fact, they are responsible for developing a coordinated communication strategy, strengthening the identity of H2IOSC and making the project recognizable and memorable.

The first objectives that its members have set themselves are the following:

- Plan to promote H2IOSC research activities and results;
- Website update;
- Creation of social channels;
- Corporate image (style manual, easily usable graphic material kit, acknowledgement to be included in the made public documents);
- Template for inserting news/events on the website and promotion;
- Support for organizing H2IOSC events.

In February 2024, they also provided the first edition of the H2IOSC Project Handbook, an open and dynamic document, constantly evolving and which will be updated as required throughout the project, with the aim to provide mainly an overview of the project's state of the art for a wider audience.

To do this they are in contact with people from the Operating Units throughout the territory with whom to discuss and get updates on local dissemination and engagement activities and initiatives.

3.4 Publicity and Visual Identity

As outlined in Article 34 of Regulation (EU) 2021/241, “The recipients of Union funding shall acknowledge the origin and ensure the visibility of the Union funding, including, where applicable, by displaying the emblem of the Union and an appropriate funding statement that reads ‘funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU’, in particular when promoting the actions and their results, by providing coherent, effective and proportionate targeted information to multiple audiences, including the media and the public.” Following the Guidelines for the actions of information and communication by the implementing subjects, all the documents related to the project (reports, deliverables, presentations, administrative documents, recruitment, and procurement documents) acknowledge the origin of the funding in order to facilitate the eligibility of operations and related costs. A set of documents templates has been produced and distributed. To ensure a coherent visual identity of the project a logo has been identified.

Figure 4 - H2IOSC logo

3.5 Outreach – the H2IOSC webpage

A project web page has been implemented at the following address <https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it>.

Figure 5 - H2IOSC webpage sections

The main sections and their contents have been implemented as shown in the table below.

SECTION	CONTENT
Homepage	Welcome page with an overview of the project
News	News items relevant to the project activities, results, or stakeholders
The Project	Project (objectives, context), WPs description
Partner Institutions	A short description of the 12 Institutes involved in the project, the people involved and the link to their official webpages

Targeted RIs	An overview of the 4 RIs involved in H2IOSC, the Italian national coordinators and the link to their web pages
Colophon	

Table 3 - The webpage structure

4. MANAGEMENT AND ADMINISTRATION

For the H2IOSC administration, the CNR procedures have been integrated with a set of project processes and procedures aimed at optimising the daily management.

4.1 Decision making

Three main decision-making structures have been envisaged to ensure the proper fulfilment of the project's objectives.

The **Administrative Management Board (AMB)**, composed by the Financial Officer of the project, the financial contact points of the involved OUs and the Infrastructure Manager. It is in charge of day-to-day coordination and timely conduct of the project.

The **Project Management Board (PMB)**, chaired by the Scientific Coordinator and composed by the Infrastructure Manager, the Financial Officer and the National Coordinators of the participating RIs, or their deputies, up to a delegation of 2 people for each RI, expressing only one vote and the CNR-DSU Director or his/her deputy. The PMB approves the work plan, discussing and changing the OUs (if required) and modifying the budget allocation within OUs and IR (if required). The PMB meets at least twice a year. In order to get a frequent update of each OU's activities and status of work in the WPs, PMB remote conferences can be held on a regular basis. This is to enable early detection of any problems, delays, and to take appropriate measures in the case of possible risks. During the PMB meetings, each WP leader is requested to briefly present his/her contribution according to the objectives, as initially planned, and WP leaders are requested to give a status report of the WP activities and progress.

The **External Advisory Board (EAB)**, performs international-level advice and evaluation both on the quality of the services provided by H2IOSC and on the quality of the users allowed to access the RI and possibly to align the project to the researchers' needs and expectations. The EAB meets at least once a year.

With regard to the latter Board, the PMB approved the "*Terms of Reference*" in order to define in more detail the mandate of its members for the entire duration of the H2IOSC project and the internal functioning with the aim to facilitate interaction with the PMB. More specifically, the above-mentioned Terms of Reference establish that:

- EAB is composed by maximum ten representatives of the main stakeholders in the field of research on Social and Cultural Innovation domain of the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI), of which: 2 delegates designated by CLARIN, 2 delegates designated by DARIAH, 2 delegates designated by E-RIHS, 2 delegates designated by OPERAS, 1 delegate representing ICDI and 1 delegate representing EOSC.
- EAB advises the PMB on any matters which may affect the scientific and technical activities of the H2IOSC project (including management, research, education, innovation, and knowledge transfer).

- PMB establishes the reviews to be performed by the EAB at its next meeting. The questions from the PMB are transmitted to the EAB Chairperson.
- PMB appoints the Chairperson and a Vice-Chairperson of the EAB from among the current appointed members. Unless the PMB decides otherwise, the EAB Chairperson or the Vice-Chairperson are invited to attend the meetings of the PMB as observers.
- EAB Chairperson convenes the meeting and decides the agenda in agreement with the requested reviews by the PMB. If needed the EAB Chairperson may convene extraordinary EAB meetings. The EAB meetings are organized online and, if needed, in person. Whenever deemed necessary to gain relevant information, its sessions are open to H2IOSC project members.
- For specific issues and problems of particular interest and/or criticality, experts on the subject are invited to participate in EAB meetings for consultation.

During the meeting held on 14 December 2023, the PMB appointed the members of the External Advisory Board as per the following:

- CLARIN (Darja Fišer and Andreas Witt);
- E-RIHS (Claire Pacheco and Julian D. Richards);
- OPERAS (Pierre Mounier and Stefano Bianco);
- DARIAH (Nicholas Larrousse and Sally Chambers);
- EOSC (Suzanne Dumouchel).

At the February 2024 General Meeting, Suzanne Dumouchel was appointed Chairperson of the EAB.

4.2 The Internal Agreement

Rights, duties, and liabilities of the partners have been set up at an early stage in an Internal Agreement undersigned by the Directors of each Institute.

In the Agreement, dated 17th October 2022, the parties indicate and designate the CNR-ISPC as Lead Institute, with the role of supporting the Financial Officer in the collection, management and preparation of the documentation required for the interim and final financial reporting to be produced to the Ministry; supporting the Scientific Coordinator in the management of activities and scientific reporting; cash the MUR payments for the entire organisation; manage the funds to be allocated to the Institutes according with the principle of sound financial management; promptly transfer the due amounts to the Institutes.

The OUs indicate their Scientific and Administrative Coordinators and undertake to carry out, each within its own sphere of competence, the activities specifically resulting from the Project in accordance with the terms, the breakdown of activities and the time schedule indicated in the project proposal (Annex B1 and Annex B2), as well as the revisions that may be required during the course of the project, which will be subject to approval by the Ministry of Universities and Research and in accordance with the provisions of Notice no. 3264 dated 28/12/2021 and the Cost Reporting Rules prepared by the MUR.

In the event of failure to comply with the deadlines, the Parties undertake to promptly notify the Scientific Coordinator and the Financial Officer, who will inform the Ministry. Without prejudice to the Parties' joint and several liability towards the MUR, each Party shall perform the services for which it is responsible in complete financial and operational autonomy and shall be responsible towards the other Parties for the perfect execution of the project part for which it is responsible. Within the limits of the obligations undertaken and as provided for in the project, the Parties undertake to make every reasonable effort for the realisation of the project and to give each other maximum assistance in its execution.

If one of the Parties is no longer able to complete the project activities for which it is responsible, the other Parties shall take over the remaining activities, according to their capacities and competencies, and the management of the relevant funds.

4.3 Guidelines for the Recruitment of Personnel

Following the Italian national legislation and the internal regulations of CNR, the *“Guidelines for the recruitment procedures of temporary staff to be employed within the NRRP-RI project Italian Open Science Cloud for the Humanities and Cultural Heritage H2IOSC”* have been drafted with the purpose of providing the administrative and scientific contact persons with some useful indications on the fulfilment of the procedures for the recruitment of temporary staff to be employed in the activities envisaged in the framework of the project. Templates of the documents to be used have been drafted both in Italian and English.

4.4 Documents and templates for the NRRP procurement procedures

Within the CNR Directorate General, a unit of purpose (UTS) "Procurement PNRR" has been established for the management of activities related to the implementation of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan and to support the institutes involved in the relevant projects in the design and execution of procurement procedures.

The UTS has drafted for the use of the whole CNR the documents shown in Figure 6 integrating the Italian Public Contract Code (Legislative Decree n. 50/2016 and Legislative Decree n. 36/2023) with the requirements of the NRRP. It has also drafted the guidelines on the DNSH principle and its respect within the NRRP funded projects, providing technical sheets relating to each sector of intervention and verification and control checklists for each sector of intervention, that briefly summarize the main checking required in the corresponding technical sheet.

The screenshot shows the 'intranet' portal of the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche. The main navigation bar includes 'Intranet', 'Area Personale', 'Istituti', and 'Ente'. The user is identified as 'danielamaria.palama' with a 'Logout' option. The page title is 'Documenti - PNRR Documenti Codice dei contratti di cui al D.lgs. 50/2016'. A left sidebar menu lists various resources like 'Benvenuto', 'Accesso e navigazione', 'Servizi informatici dell'Ente', 'Risorse comuni', 'Logo CNR', 'Documenti - PNRR', 'Codice D.lgs. 50/2016', 'Codice D.lgs. 36/2023', 'Acquisti nuovo Codice', 'Progetti PON', 'PON Infrastrutture', 'PON 12 Aree', and 'Elezioni RSU 2022'. The main content area is titled 'Documenti supporto acquisti' and lists several documents for download, including 'Linee guida 10/03/2023 GDL Procurement PNRR (.pdf)', 'Procedura aperta sopra soglia mono lotto documentazione di gara (.zip)', 'Procedura aperta sopra soglia multi lotto documentazione di gara (.zip)', 'Affidamento diretto (documentazione) (.zip)', 'Guida sintetica alla documentazione antimafia (.zip)', 'Procedura negoziata ex D.L. 76_2020 sotto soglia (.zip)', 'Procedura negoziata ex art. 63 infungibilità? (.zip)', 'Linee Guida per le procedure negoziate (.pdf)', 'Guida alla verifica dei requisiti OE stranieri 160323 (.pdf)', and 'LineeGuida DNSH DO NO SIGNIFICANT HARM 18/04/2023 (.zip)'. A 'Bandi' section lists 'Bando a cascata e allegati (.zip)'.

Figure 6 - NRRP Procurement templates CNR

5. MONITORING

For the successful execution of the H2IOSC activities plan (Figure and achievement of IO, a daily and thorough monitoring process is considered strategic. The short time range for the implementation of the activities, the need to meet targets and milestones set by the EC (30th June 2023 for the recruitment of the Infrastructure Manager and 31st December 2023 for the identification of the implementing parties, i.e., suppliers of goods and services/executors of works) and the achievement of the project objectives required the integration of different monitoring activities and the engaged cooperation of the involved applicants.

Figure 7 H2IOSC Gantt chart

In order to track, review, report and, if needed, adjust on the project’s performance a set of tools have been implemented.

5.1 Integrated System for the Accounting Management

From an accounting-administrative point of view, CNR is equipped with a computerized recording and storage system of accounting data through which it is possible to obtain both prints and data extractions: SIGLA is an Integrated System for the Accounting Management that allows the management control (including the flow) of financial resources and aligns the internal accounting management with the reporting criteria of research projects to which CNR participates.

Moreover, in line with the European system and to improve the connection within the Public Administration’s accounts, CNR adopts in its financial statement the integrated chart of accounts consistent with the provisions of the D.P.R. 4/10/13 n.132. General directives and provisions of Law 6 November 2012 n. 190 are published within the institutional website section "[Transparent Administration](#)", currently being updated to incorporate the changes introduced by Legislative Decree 25 May 2016 n. 97 (GU General Series N. 132 of 08/06/2016). In the specific sub-section "[Competition announcements and contracts](#)", in compliance with the provisions of the law, tender notices and summary tables - made freely available in an open standard digital format - are published.

5.2 Sharepoint Workbook

Using the Microsoft Teams™ app *Sharepoint*, available for all the CNR employees, an Excel workbook with the financial details of the project has been shared with the participants. The

workbook consists of some sheets (Institutes budget, Institutes monitoring, Activities budget, Activities monitoring, Recruitment Monitoring, Procurement Monitoring, Reporting, Personnel reporting, Personnel hours). The first sheets provide an at-a-glance picture of the budget structure and costs categories, arranged by OU, activity. The monitoring sheets is populated by each OU with the details of every single planned purchase (description, selected tendering procedure and financial/administrative details and references), allowing to monitor the incurred costs and possible deviations from the planned budget (including possible use of project savings due to changes in the market prices).

5.3 OwnCloud repository

The control on the eligibility of expenses is performed through a check on the documents related to the purchase and recruitment procedures. To ensure a smooth flow of documents, the H2IOSC partners have agreed to use the CNRBox cloud storage based on OwnCloud, an open-source software running on servers located at the CNR headquarters in Rome. A dedicated folder (Figure 8) has been created and structured with folders of common interest, accessible to all the participants, and one folder for each OU, accessible to the Infrastructure Manager, the Scientific Coordinator, the Financial Officer and the personnel working for the Unit. In the Units folders, four different folders contain all the administrative documents related to a) the provision of the facilities, b) the recruitment procedures, c) the purchase procedures, and d) the bi-monthly financial reporting.

Figure 8 - OwnCloud repository structure

5.4 Scientific repository

The control on the reports and deliverables is performed through a check on their content compared to what is requested in the project proposal (Annex B1 and Annex B2) and on the timescales set out in the aforementioned annexes and/or defined by the Project Management of H2IOSC. In order to allow the continuous exchange of information and the contextual viewing of documents, the H2IOSC partners have agreed to use, for the first months of project activity and until the end of 2023, the Google Workspace instance provided by the OVI and thus named “Vocabolario”, and then move on to Microsoft Teams™ app, maintaining the same structure previously adopted.

Among the available tools offered by the platform, easily customizable by the users (Figure 9) a dedicated folder named H2IOSC (Figure 10) has been created and structured with folders of common interest and one folder for each WP, accessible to the Infrastructure Manager, the Scientific Coordinator, the Financial Officer, the WP Leaders and the Activity Leaders. In the WPs folders, the bimonthly reports on the activity progress by the Activity leaders, the semestral reports by the RI coordinators and the deliverables by the WP leaders are uploaded.

Figure 9 – Microsoft Teams Workspace

Figure 10 – Microsoft Teams repository

6. REPORTING

The reporting process workflow has been established following the different time schedule of the procedural and financial reports. The procedural report is an ongoing process that has to be implemented on the platform on a daily basis as long as the recruiting and procurement contracts are signed, while the financial report has to be submitted early on the first month following the reported bimester. To facilitate the correct implementation of both reports, a set of tools have been developed and shared with the OUs.

6.1 Checklists (Annex 6 and 7)

According to the requests contained in the Guidelines for Reporting on Investment in Research Infrastructures - M4C2, the Implementing Institutions shall produce, through the GEA IT reporting system, the technical progress reports, the deliverables, the list of incurred expenses, as well as the self-monitoring checklists, according to the models made available by the Ministry. With specific reference to the procedures carried out for the purpose of selecting suppliers and/or external personnel, the Parties in charge of such procedures shall carry out a self-monitoring through specific Checklists annexed to the Guidelines (see Annex 6 and Annex 7). To facilitate the filling in of the checklists and ensure consistent and complete information content the H2IOSC Financial Manager has provided the Institutes with a pre-filled template of the checklists, with all the common references and the requested details for the single procedures. Each Institute shall promptly provide a checklist, signed by the Institute Director, for every completed procedure once the contracts have been signed.

6.2 Reporting factsheet

To facilitate the filling of the financial reporting on the GEA portal, a reporting factsheet has been produced and shared with the OUs. The factsheet, an excel file composed of 4 sheets (procedural recruitment, financial recruitment, procedural procurement, financial procurement) faithfully reproduces the sections of GEA and the information required therein. Part of the sections has to be compiled with the details of the single procedures while other are auto filled.

6.3 Timesheet

The timesheet was developed by implementing the basic structure and architecture of a timesheet template in .xlsx (Excel) format consisting only of the monthly details of the hours. As shown in Figure 11 other sheets were linked to it.

Figure 11 - General structure of the Timesheet file

In the “Instructions” sheet, there are instructions for the correct filling in of Timesheets.

In the “Riepilogo” sheet, the personnel unit information must be entered. Some information can be selected from the drop-down menu. The data are directly reported in the monthly Timesheets and in the declaration DSAN sheet.

U.O. PARTECIPANTE (Participant Unit)
Nominativo Personale (Person name)
Matricola (Employee number)
Profilo e livello (Profile and level)
WP ed attività (WP and activity)

In the “DSAN” sheet some data are directly reported from “Riepilogo” (recap) sheet and the missing information must be entered.

Every two months, the declaration with the related monthly Timesheets, must be sent by the employees to the administrative staff for the Director's signature.

Information on the productive time spent by the staff unit must be entered in the individual monthly sheets indicating the hours actually worked as from the time recording system of the CNR (ePAS – electronic Personnel Attendance System) also reporting absences and permits.

All the information reported in the "Reporting factsheets" as well as that highlighted in the reports on the physical progress of the project are reported in the dedicated sections of the GEA portal by the H2IOSC project staff authorized to do so.

6.4 Workflow

In order to facilitate the partners in the preparation of administrative and financial documents as well as reports and deliverables in compliance with the defined and/or agreed deadlines, the H2IOSC Project Management implemented descriptive workflows and templates (deliverable template and project report template) on the procedural, financial and physical progress of the project. Below there is a description of the aforementioned workflows.

6.4.1 Procedural workflow

The following Figure 12 outlines the timing and actors involved in the preparation, submission and signing of checklists 6 and 7, in the preparation of the reporting factsheet implemented to facilitate the compilation of the procedural progress section of the GEA portal, as well as in the updating of the administrative and financial documentation uploaded to OwnCloud.

Figure 12 – Procedural workflow

6.4.2 Financial workflow

The following Figure 13 outlines the timing and actors involved in the preparation, submission and signing of timesheet and DSAN, in the preparation of the reporting factsheet implemented to facilitate the compilation of the financial progress section of the GEA portal, in the signature of the Annex 1 with the list of the incurred expenses, as well as in the updating of the documentation uploaded to OwnCloud.

FINANCIAL PROGRESS OF THE PROJECT BY DAY 2 OF THE MONTH FOLLOWING THE REFERENCE BIMONTHLY PERIOD	
Recruited staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fills out, signs and sends timesheet for the reference bimonthly period to the Activity Referent - Fills out DSAN and sends it to the Administrative Coordinator of the OU
Activity Referent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Signs timesheet and sends it to the Administrative Coordinator of the OU
Administrative Coordinator of each OU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Submits DSANs for the Director's signature - Fills out reporting factsheet (financial sheets) - Verifies that the documentation in OwnCloud is updated with the relevant supporting documents signed DSAN and timesheet
Director of each OU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Signs DSAN - Signs, together with all the other Directors Annex 1 with the list of the incurred expenses for the reference bimonthly period

Figure 13 – Financial workflow

6.4.3 Physical workflow

The following Figure 14 outlines the timing and actors involved in the preparation, uploading to the relevant Project folder, as well as in the checking and consequent uploading to GEA of the expected project deliverables.

Indeed, as regards the approval of the deliverables, the process defined by the H2IOSC Project Management provides that the WP Leader is the person responsible for preparing the document. The Scientific Coordinator must verify that the content of the deliverable complies with the provisions contained in the project proposal (Annex B1 and Annex B2) and then proceed with uploading it to the GEA portal. The Infrastructure Manager supports the Scientific Coordinator in this activity also by monitoring that the process is completed within the agreed terms.

PHYSICAL PROGRESS OF THE PROJECT : Deliverables

Figure 14 – Deliverables workflow

The deliverable template was prepared on the project's letterhead and with references to the logos provided for advertising the intervention financed by the European Union – Next Generation EU funds. It includes an introductory part with references to the project, to the deliverable produced and its expected and actual delivery date, as well as to its authors. The template also includes a section dedicated to possible figures and tables, one dedicated to the content part in line with the provisions of the project technical sheet, one to the conclusions and finally one to the references.

To ensure that all deliverables produced meet high quality standards, a common set of requirements has been identified:

Specific: The information provided must be clear and unambiguous. It should be coherent with the information requested in Annex B1 and Annex B2.

Correctness: The information provided must be evidence-based, consistent, complete and accurate.

Relevance: The information provided must be focused on key issues adapted to its target audience.

The following Figures 15 and 16 outline the timing and actors involved in the preparation and uploading of the referred reports to the relevant Project folder, as well as in the checking and consequent uploading to GEA of the expected project information.

PHYSICAL PROGRESS OF THE PROJECT : Bimonthly reports

<p>OU Responsible per Raka Activity leader</p>	<p>IN CONJUNCTION WITH THE ACTIVITIES PERFORMANCE prepares the report for each OU/WP, populating, for the reference bimonthly period, the relevant section of the Internal report, called "Activity Detail" of the relevant folder (WP) (content in line with the provisionsof the project technical sheet)</p>
<p>WP Leader</p>	<p>15 DAYS BEFORE THE END OF THE REFERENCE BIMONTHLY PERIOD checks the reports produced by the Activity Leaders for the reference WP; populates the sections of the Internal Report called "Workpackage details", "Intermediate objectives details", "Conclusions" in the reference folder (WP) (content in line with the provisionsof the project technical sheet)</p>
<p>Scientific Coordinator</p>	<p>BY THE CLOSE OF THE REFERENCE BIMONTHLY PERIOD</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - checks the content of the uploaded reports and interacts with the WP leaders for any clarifications/integrations - Uploads the information to GEA

Figure 15 – Bimonthly reports workflow

PHYSICAL PROGRESS OF THE PROJECT : Six-monthly reports

<p>RI Coordinator</p>	<p>WITHIN THE 15 DAYS FOLLOWING THE REFERENCE SEMESTER for each WP, populates (for his/her RI) the section of the Internal Report called "Research Infrastructure implementation report" - Current state of alignment to the H2IOSC federation reached by each RI, including aspects related to the technological, ICT and scientific issues addressed by the reference WP (according to Annex C) - based on the reports produced by the Activity Leaders relating to his/her RI</p>
<p>Scientific Coordinator</p>	<p>verifies the content of the RI reports on each WP (section of the Internal Report called "Research Infrastructure implementation report" and interacts with the RI Coordinators for any clarifications/integrationsto finalizethe documents</p>

Figure 16 – Six-months reports workflow

The report template was prepared on the project's letterhead and with references to the logos provided for advertising the intervention financed by the European Union – Next Generation

EU funds. It includes an introductory part with references to the project, to the semester of reference, as well as to its authors.

The template also includes the following listed sections, where description of the progress of the activities compared to the project technical sheet, any critical issues, the KPIs and KPRs in relation to the intermediate objectives are requested:

- *Research Infrastructure implementation report*, for which the coordinator of the concerned RI is responsible;
- *Workpackage details, Intermediate objectives details and Conclusions*, for which the WP leaders involved in the RI concerned are responsible;
- *Activity Detail*, for which the Activity leaders of the WPs involved in the RI concerned are responsible.

7. ETHICS POLICY

The staff involved in the activities of the H2IOSC project operates in compliance with the ethical and deontological principles and values that fall within the scope of Research Integrity, as described in the scientific literature and in the main international Charters and Conventions, as well as in the "Guidelines for the Research Integrity" produced by the CNR, approved on 10 June 2015 and updated in 2019².

"Research Integrity" means the set of ethical principles and values, obligations and professional standards that constitute the basis of the responsible and correct conduct of those who must carry out, finance or evaluate scientific research, as well as the institutions that promote and carry out it. The application of these principles and values is fundamental to guarantee the quality of research and enhance the reputation and public image of science.

In this regard, the CNR has established an independent body, called "CNR Research Ethics and Integrity Committee", with a consultative role charged, among other things, with providing advice on research ethics, evaluating the ethical issues of research projects, with developing and implementing a plan for the prevention and verification of research misconduct and the provision of ethical advice for the management of cases of research misconduct.

The fundamental principles for the integrity of research are: dignity, responsibility, fairness, rectitude and diligence to which other principles are connected, such as those of scientific freedom, the reputation of individuals and loyalty towards others and towards institutions, honesty and objectivity in the conduct of research, independence of judgment, reciprocity and cooperation with others in carrying out one's tasks, impartiality and efficiency in the use of resources, as well as social responsibility.

In light of the above, the standards for ethics and professional conduct that all staff involved in the H2IOSC project activities are required to implement are the following:

- to maintain the highest moral standards irrespective of the difficulties and limitations that at any moment might be raised;

² <https://www.cnr.it/en/ethics>

- to develop or manage all activities and their results in a fair and transparent manner for all participants;
- to share ideas and information, use instruments of known accuracy, maintain professional moderation in the conduct and give due credit to the contributions of others;
- to treat colleagues respectfully and as equals, and through cooperative actions diffuse knowledge by both teaching and learning without prejudice against others, treating them likewise irrespective of gender, nationality, ethnicity, religion, age, sexual orientation, gender expression, presence of disabilities, educational background, professional origin or other personal attributes or aspects through which diversity manifests itself;
- to respect and protect life and the environment avoiding any aggression and following the highest health and safety standards, including the disposal of waste;
- to solve possible conflicts in a friendly and respectful manner towards colleagues, involving, where necessary, the appropriate bodies established at Project and Institution level.

8. DATA ACCESS POLICY

As regards the open access policy, the H2IOSC project community follows guidelines that respond to the principles of the European Charter for the free circulation of knowledge, with which the entire CNR conforms.³

Besides the official sign of the “Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities”⁴, CNR is, indeed, involved in several cooperation actions and initiatives held in collaboration with international research institutions with the aim of contributing to the definition of the best strategies and policies for a free open access to scientific information.

As reported on the institutional website of the CNR⁵, Open Access to publicly funded research outputs (publications and data) enhances the circulation of knowledge, supports innovation, the transfer of knowledge, the competitiveness, internationalization and quality of research, thus fostering economic, social and cultural benefits for enterprises (particularly small and medium-sized enterprises), for the public sector and generally speaking for citizens at large. To support the Open Access model and support the development of specific policies on a national level, on March 2013 the presidents of the main Italian Research bodies -CRUI, CNR, ENEA, INFN, INGV and ISS- signed a 'Position statement' on Open Access to research outputs in Italy. In this way, Italian partners demonstrated the common will to undertake concrete initiatives to put the European Commission Recommendation on open access to scientific knowledge (17 luglio 2012) into practice.

In addition, considering that H2IOSC is the Italian Cloud Network for research in humanities, linguistics and heritage science which foresees the collaboration of the Italian nodes of 2 ESFRI

³ <https://www.cnr.it/en/cnr-open-access>

⁴ <https://openaccess.mpg.de/Berlin-Declaration>

⁵ <https://www.cnr.it/en/position-statement>

Landmarks in Social and Cultural Innovation (CLARIN and DARIAH ERICs) and 2 Projects in the same domain (E-RIHS, OPERAS), its community is inspired by the principles and guidelines for access and related services established by the “European Charter for access to research infrastructures” of the European Commission.

For greater detail regarding the guidelines on managing data relating to open access, please refer to deliverable D3.1 "Guidelines for data, services, software platform policy implementation" which includes a specific section dedicated to policies about Open Data and the frameworks enabling Open Access according to academic best practices and EU recommendations.

9. IP MANAGEMENT ORGANIZATION

When it comes to intellectual property, it is essential to distinguish between what is intellectual property, i.e. key assets, and what is instead intellectual property rights, i.e. legal tools to support commercial exploitation.

Intellectual Property Rights, are exclusive rights, which allow the owner to prevent competitors from using these intangible assets. To do so it is, therefore, important that the Intellectual Property asset be protected, managed and enforced.

Figure 17 – Intellectual Property Rights ⁶

More specifically, Intellectual Property rights grant a monopoly on the intellect creation for a limited amount of time depending on the type of right that is protected.

- Copyrights 70 years after the death of the author;
- Patents 20 years after the application;

⁶ Figure from the EU "Horizon Results Platform & European IP Helpdesk" presentation 14/03/2024 Introduction to "Intellectual Property as a Business Asset"

- Industrial designs 25 five years after the registration;
- Trademarks indefinitely as long as renewal fees are payed.

Ownership of intellectual property guarantee important added values which translates, for instance, into: enhance the reputation, attract funding and investment, being leveraged in many different ways.

For these reasons, it is essential that also within the H2IOSC project, which is currently only participated by CNR institutes but which, for the carrying out of its project activities within the Next Generation EU and in the future, will see relationships with different public and private entities, the management of the Background and Foreground be defined and regulated.

Taking into account that by Background we mean information, techniques, Know-how, software and materials (regardless of the form or medium in which they are disclosed or stored) held by CNR prior to the conclusion of the Project Agreement, or acquired in parallel with it, as well as copyrights, other IP rights, or rights pertaining to such information, techniques, know-how, software and materials following applications for, or the issue of, patents, designs, supplementary protection certificates or similar forms of protection. And that by Foreground we mean the results, including information, whether or not they can be protected, arising from the Project, as well as copyrights and other IP and know-how or rights pertaining to such results following applications for, or the issue of patents, designs, supplementary protection certificates or similar forms of protection.

In this regard, please refer to what is expressly established by "*Regolamento per la generazione, gestione e valorizzazione della proprietà industriale sui risultati della ricerca del CNR*" approved by the CNR Board of Directors on 19 December 2019, although it must be considered that this regulation will soon be modified to adapt its provisions to the provisions of Italian law no. 102/2023, containing amendments to the industrial property code (Italian legislative decree n. 30/2005), which entirely modified the art. 65 governing the ownership of industrial property rights of researchers' inventions.

Article 65 of the industrial property code now provides that "*when the industrial invention is made in the execution or fulfilment of a contract or relationship of work or employment, even if for a fixed term, with a university, including a legally recognized non-state one, a public research body or a scientific hospitalization and treatment institute, as well as in the framework of an agreement between the same subjects, rights coming from the invention belong to the institution to which the inventor belongs*", except for the right of the latter to be recognized as the author. The rights deriving from the invention created in the execution of research activities carried out by a public research body, therefore, are governed by agreements stipulated for this purpose between the parties, drawn up on the basis of specific Guidelines defined by the inter-ministerial decree - Ministero delle Imprese e del Made in Italy and Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca - which identify the specific principles and criteria for the regulation of contractual relationships, when the object of the agreement is a commissioned research activity, i.e. research financed, in whole or in part, by third parties other than Public research bodies, which are carried out according to a purpose driven by the financing entity to respond to its needs.

The agreement between the parties must be stipulated prior to the start of the collaboration activity, in order to define ab origine all aspects of the relationship, including the object and purpose of the agreement, the background and foreground regime, the regulation of confidentiality/methods of communication of results, regulation of publications.

Unless otherwise agreed by the parties, the Background remains the property of the sole owner who developed it (Institution and any third party). Where the use of the foreground following the completion of the research activity presupposes continued access to the Institution's background, it is recommended that the agreement also establishes the conditions for access to this background by the financing entity in the event of commercial exploitation of the foreground. In this case, access may be granted through a license.

As regards, however, the Foreground, given the provisions of the new art. 65 previously reported, several alternative scenarios can be hypothesized regarding ownership of the results and related exploitation: a) co-ownership of the results between the Institution and the financing entity; b) exclusive ownership of the Institution; c) exclusive ownership of the financing entity.

- a) A situation of joint ownership of the results can arise both when both parties have contributed to achieving the inventive result, and when the parties have contractually established the onset of a situation of joint ownership.
- b) A situation of exclusive ownership of the Institution occurs above all when the inventive result is achieved entirely by the researcher or group of researchers of the Institution.
- c) A situation of exclusive ownership of the financing entity occurs when the expected knowledge is not particularly innovative.

In the case of agreements which have as their object *service activities*, in which the financing entity asks the Institution to carry out a standard activity, with the use of consolidated and routine technological skills or capabilities, the expected results are represented by data and scientific reports that are unlikely to be the subject of possible patents and are therefore usually the exclusive property of the financing entity. In this case, it is appropriate for the parties to regulate the possibility for the Institution to use the data deriving from the service activity for the purposes of further research or for teaching activities.

In the case of agreements concerning *development activities*, in which the financing entity has independently conceived the project idea that will be developed within the scope of the collaboration, or has created the technology that is intended to be applied and asks the Institution for a qualified intervention aimed at optimisation, validation, refinement or completion of the idea/technology; or for agreements concerning *innovative research activities*, in which the Institution's innovation contribution is particularly significant, there could be exclusive ownership of the results by the Institution, or joint ownership with the financing entity, and it is appropriate that the agreement between the parties provides for the methods of transfer of the results to the financing entity. The transfer can take place through the assignment of patent applications that the Institution (alone or jointly with the financing entity) will have filed or already granted patents.

In relation to the actual innovation activity, when the background and foreground contribution of the Institution is more significant and the innovation cannot be considered as a simple expansion of the background knowledge of the parties (both in the case of exclusive ownership by the Institution and in the case of joint ownership), two access methods can be configured in favor of the financing entity: there could be a transfer of the results or an exclusive license, which will concern the entire ownership or share of the Institution.

For what concerns the regulation of collaboration between the Institution and the financing entity: the information exchanged between the parties during the implementation of the agreement is subject to confidentiality, with the exception of that information which is in the public domain at the date of the agreement; which are in the possession of the parties even though they have not been provided directly or indirectly by the other party; which have become public knowledge subsequent to the date of the agreement due to causes independent of fault of the parties themselves, or that they were legitimately revealed by a third party who had free access to them, without constraints of secrecy.

The documentation developed in implementation of the agreement may be, in whole or in part, the subject of scientific publications subject to written agreement between the parties. They may provide that, in the event that the request for publication comes from the Institution, prior authorization from the financing entity is necessary, which reserves the right to evaluate any damage to it resulting from disclosure. In case of authorisation, a citation of the financing entity as promoter may also be envisaged. In each case, any lack of consent from the financing entity who completely denies publication must always be promptly justified and must occur within certain times to be defined in advance in the contractual context. The parties will be able to evaluate whether to include silent consent mechanisms in the agreement in the event of a request for publication to the financing party.

Another important aspect to take into consideration in projects like H2IOSC, which share the European principles of open access is the following.

Open Science does not affect the intellectual property generated by the research results and is based on an adequate management of intellectual property. Beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements related to scientific publications. The decision on whether to seek protection for intellectual property rights is made before deciding whether or not to publish results. Therefore, when aiming at patent protection, research results can only be published after the patent application has been filed. The protection of research results and their commercial exploitation (for example through patenting) is therefore guaranteed. Open access to research data follows the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. Projects may decide not to provide open access to research data if it goes against the beneficiaries' legitimate interests or due to other justified reasons (e.g. confidentiality or security concerns).

In addition, an aspect to carefully consider is that concerning the protection of intellectual property in relation to the data managed and provided by H2IOSC for its purposes.

Indeed, H2IOSC provides its user community with common access to instruments and scientific data through unified entry points and harmonised procedures. It is not the owner

but facilitates the sharing and reuse of research data produced and exchange of knowledge in general.

It is important to prevent situations where the sharing and re-use of research data by the H2IOSC participating Institutes/RIs national nodes or other researchers made available through H2IOSC inadvertently breach the rights of data owners or third parties' IPR (mainly copyright). This is because the way in which research data is produced and described may automatically create copyrights if the description contains a creative element (hence rendering the data "copyrightable").

For this purpose, we carried out an analysis on the guidelines applied by the four research infrastructures (in particular at national level), not forgetting, however, that H2IOSC participating Institutes belong to the same Italian public research body (CNR) and which as such are required to comply with the regulations defined at the level of the Body in compliance with national legislation.

E-RIHS facilitates the sharing of its scientific results with the user community, among others, through a system of open licensing (CC BY recommended). In justified cases, Open Access principles should be balanced against legal restrictions and legitimate interests. These types of measures may include embargo periods (i.e. periods of time where an access restriction is applied to a piece of data and/or other research output, whereby the item will not be made available as Open Access until a predetermined time), authorisation procedures, specific contractual arrangements and licenses other than those recommended by the RI.

CLARIN prefers open data and open source software, but whenever there may be legal or legitimate reasons to retain access and re-use of data or parts of it restricted, CLARIN ensures that users must authenticate and sign a license (<https://dspace-clarin-it.ilc.cnr.it/repository/xmlui/page/licenses>) in order to download the concerned data. More specifically, metadata are always publicly available, while restrictive licences could be granted for bitstreams or embargo periods on those data.

DARIAH-IT's licensing approach follows a tiered structure. For search results, the metadata is published in an "as free as possible" mode using the Creative Commons License 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication (CC 0). This allows for maximum reusability and distribution. The default licensing choice for most content remains Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike (CC BY-NC-SA). This strikes a balance between attribution, reuse restrictions, and fostering collaborative scholarship within the humanities community. DARIAH-IT's data management practices and licensing agreements are subject to periodic review and update to ensure alignment with evolving needs and requirements.

OPERAS policies encourage and promote compliance with the FAIR principles and the Open Science paradigm in its various articulations: Open Access, Open Data, Open Innovation. In particular, OPERAS supports consistent alignment in this area through the adoption of the CC BY 4.0 Deed – Attribution 4.0 International License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>) for the sharing and use of publications and other digital objects/materials and their metadata. This license allows re-users to distribute, remix, adapt and build upon the material in any medium or format, as long as the creator is

credited. OPERAS also recognises the possible need for different licensing types in both directions of the openness spectrum. In particular, it recognises that researchers from the H2IOSC community might express preferences or needs that differ from those embedded in the CC-BY License. A wider-ranging commitment is thus oriented to the use of Open Culture licences (<https://creativecommons.org/about/arts-culture/>).

10. QUALITY PLAN

In order to guarantee the success of the H2IOSC project it is necessary to ensure a high level of quality of the project with respect to different types of public, at an internal and external level, i.e. in relation to the project team, on the one hand, and to interested parties, users and third parties, on the other. For this reason, this quality plan must not be considered as a bureaucratic compliance verification exercise but rather as a collaborative process between all parties involved.

A quality plan should include, at least, the following information:

- Goals in terms of quality;
- Quality approach and processes that we propose to analyze;
- Control activities and tools to use;
- Subjects involved in quality control.

Goals in terms of quality

By adopting this quality plan, we intend to evaluate the efficiency of the project, i.e. how much H2IOSC is an effective project and what the value is perceived by its community and external parties and, therefore, its level of satisfaction. The final objective is to aim to produce improvements to the processes adopted and the services provided, carry out and improve project planning also basing it on data emerging from this investigation, obtain information to help the decision-making process, react more promptly to any critical issues, ensure efficient use of the resources allocated.

Quality approach and processes that we propose to analyze

Below are the four areas that we identified for the purposes of our quality survey, taking into account that this quality plan aims to analyze only aspects and processes that are relevant during the duration of the project as financed by the NRRP. Once this phase is concluded, it will be necessary to build a different quality plan that should be more in line with the implementation/executive phase and capable of being adapted in consideration of new needs that may arise.

1. Quality assessment of internal procedures and processes

It aims at evaluating the existence and correctness of the H2IOSC's internal processes, including governance, management and administration, as well as their implementation and adequacy with respect to the objectives of the project, the

obligations towards the Italian Ministry of the University and Research and their compliance with the applicable European regulations.

2. Quality assessment of interactions between WPs and RIs

It aims to evaluate, on the one hand, whether the activities and results obtained within each work package meet the expectations and needs of the Research Infrastructures involved, and on the other, whether the strategic objectives and operational indications of execution are established and communicated clearly from RIs to work packages.

3. Quality assessment of the results of WPs activities

It aims to evaluate the outcomes of the work packages with an eye towards the future of the project community, taking into account that the actual evaluation from a technical-scientific point of view of the WPs activities is assigned by the Italian Ministry to an external technical-scientific expert.

4. Quality assessment of the services offered

It aims to examine the importance of such services for the aims of H2IOSC, their adhesion to H2IOSC core values and the expected/actual demand by the interested parties.

Control activities and tools to use

The tool we hypothesized to use is the questionnaire to be addressed, depending on the area to be analysed, to the entire project community, rather than to the members of the work packages and to the national coordinators of the research infrastructures involved, as well as to the External Advisory Board and users. The choice of the questionnaire, with the provision of specific questions to be answered with YES or NO and suggestion fields, was made to better respond to the need to carry out an evaluation in qualitative terms which was more subjective and which could go hand in hand with a more objective evaluation, such as that described in deliverable D.1.5 "H2IOSC Forum Report", which involves the use of dashboards developed on the basis of reports/data/documents of various types collected.

Below are therefore some examples of questions that could be included in the planned questionnaires to better respond to the goals in terms of quality described previously.

Quality assessment of internal procedures and processes – Project community

- *Is the decision-making chain clearly defined?*
- *Are responsibilities pertaining to work under H2IOSC specified?*
- *Are administrative procedures well-defined?*
- *Within the H2IOSC project are respected the adopted standards for ethics and professional conduct?*

Quality assessment of interactions between WPs and Ris – WPs members and RICs

- Is the action carried out within the WPs in line with the needs and vision of the Ris?
- Do the results obtained within the WPs provide sufficient information to outline a future line of intervention for the cluster?
- Do the WPs have all the necessary information regarding the operation of the Ris nodes to be able to finalize their activities?
- Is the strategic direction that the Ris intend to undertake clearly defined?

Quality assessment of the results of WPs activities – EAB

- Do the activities undertaken within the project go in the direction of satisfying researchers' needs and expectations?
- Are there any potential users who have not been considered and who could be included in the H2IOSC services offering? Which?
- Are there specific recommendations to follow to develop innovative activity and technology transfer?
- Is the training offer developed in the project context sufficiently exhaustive in terms of content and recipients?

Quality assessment of the services offered– Users

- Is the facility infrastructure and equipment themselves appropriate for the foreseen activities?
- Is there a central contact point for the H2IOSC activities?
- Are there information regarding data management?
- Are you satisfied with the service provided or do you have any suggestions for improvement to make? If yes, which ones?

Below is a hypothetical timeline for submitting the questionnaires which will be better defined also in relation to the definitive duration of the project and the opportunity to submit some questionnaires more than once.

Figure 18 – Timeline questionnaires

Subjects involved in quality control

For the correct implementation of the quality plan described, in addition to the recipients of the questionnaires who will be submitted, the involvement of a **Quality contact** is envisaged, who will presumably be a person within the project team not directly involved in the writing/implementation of the policies and in the provision of services in order to ensure a form of impartiality.

The Quality contact will have to take care of the submission of the questionnaires, the collection of data and the consequent sending of the results to the Project Management for the overall evaluation assessment of the quality evaluation results and recommendation for decision to PMB.

11. CONCLUSIONS

The processes described in this document, as well as the templates and guidelines prepared for use by the project community, have the objective of allowing Project Management to have control of the different phases of H2IOSC implementation, monitoring its progress, intercepting any critical issues and then adopt appropriate corrective measures.

The definition of specific workflows of the procedural, financial and physical progress processes of the project allows to clearly identify the main players and the timescales to be respected so that the Infrastructure Manager, the Scientific Coordinator and the Financial Manager, each for their own part of competence, can verify and guarantee correct compliance with the scientific, technical, administrative, financial and contractual obligations (including those relating to reporting on specific tools) established in the authorization phase of the NRRP funding.

Furthermore, the sections of the document relating to ethics, data access policy, intellectual property management have been described in compliance with the regulatory framework adopted by the CNR, in consideration of the fact that this Body is the leader of the project and all the Operating Units are its Institutes, and in any case respecting the applicable legislation.

The quality plan was designed taking into account the peculiarities of the H2IOSC project, its stakeholders and the activities envisaged in the context of the NRRP programme.

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